

Evaluating Eye Symptoms in Psoriatic Patients: A Case-control Study**Kokila Anand¹, Nidhi Patel², Neha Solanki³, Mayurkumar Pushkarbhai Dangi⁴**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Ophthalmology, GMERS Medical College attached General Hospital, Rajpipla, Gujarat, India²Junior Resident, GMERS Medical College attached General Hospital, Rajpipla, Gujarat, India³Dermatologist, GMERS Medical College attached General Hospital, Rajpipla, Gujarat, India⁴Senior Resident, Department of Ophthalmology, GMERS Medical College attached General Hospital, Rajpipla, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

Background: Psoriasis is a persistent inflammatory condition that primarily impacts the skin, nails, and joints. While ocular manifestations are relatively uncommon in the existing literature, particularly among those with psoriatic arthritis. This study aimed to investigate the prevalence and characteristics of eye involvement in individuals diagnosed with psoriasis.

Materials and Methods: The study included 134 individuals with psoriasis compared with 134 healthy participants. A comprehensive history was obtained for all participants, followed by dermatological, systemic, and ophthalmological assessments. Schirmer's test and tear breakup time (BUT) were performed. Continuous variables were analyzed using the t-test, while categorical data were compared using the chi-square test. Logistic regression analysis was employed to explore associations between ocular findings and variables. Statistical evaluations were conducted separately for the right and left eyes.

Results: Patients with psoriasis exhibited a significantly higher frequency of ocular findings in both eyes compared to the control group. Additionally, Schirmer's and BUT values were markedly reduced in psoriasis patients compared to the controls.

Conclusion: The findings underscore the importance of regular ophthalmological evaluations in patients with psoriasis for timely detection and management of ocular complications. However, further research is needed to elucidate the underlying mechanisms of ocular involvement in this patient population.

Keywords: Eye, Psoriasis, Schirmer's test, Tear breakup.

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Introduction

Psoriasis is a chronic systemic inflammatory disorder with an unclear etiology. It is characterized by sharply demarcated erythematous plaques covered with silvery-white scales and affects approximately 1–3% of the global population. While primarily recognized as a dermatological condition, psoriasis can also involve extra-cutaneous manifestations, including the nails, joints, and ocular structures [1–3]. The ocular manifestations of psoriasis remain underreported and insufficiently understood in the existing literature. However, emerging data from observational studies and case reports indicate that psoriasis has the potential to cause inflammatory damage to various ocular tissues, including the eyelids, conjunctiva, cornea, and uvea. It is estimated that approximately 10% of psoriasis patients develop ocular symptoms, with a higher prevalence observed in individuals with psoriatic arthritis [4–8]. Ocular involvement in psoriasis may

arise through direct inflammatory pathways or as a secondary complication of systemic treatments used to manage the disease, such as immunosuppressive agents or biologics. The lack of routine ophthalmologic screening in patients with psoriasis may contribute to delayed diagnosis and treatment, potentially leading to preventable complications, such as vision impairment or chronic ocular discomfort [9].

In the present study, we aimed to systematically evaluate the prevalence and nature of ocular findings in patients diagnosed with psoriasis. This investigation seeks to underscore the importance of integrating routine ocular examinations into the standard care for psoriasis patients. By identifying subclinical or early ocular involvement, the study aims to facilitate timely intervention, thereby mitigating the risk of long-term complications and improving the overall quality of life for individuals affected by this multifaceted disease.

Material and Methods

This study involved 134 consecutive psoriasis patients and a control group of 134 healthy individuals. The diagnosis of psoriasis was confirmed through dermatological and histopathological evaluations. All patients underwent eye examinations at the time of their visits. Participants were excluded if they had systemic diseases known to cause ocular manifestations (like Behçet's disease, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, sarcoidosis, systemic lupus erythematosus, vasculitic conditions etc.), a history of eye surgery or trauma, primary eye diseases (like glaucoma or optic neuritis), use of contact lenses, or were under 18 years of age.

Patients provided details regarding age, sex, psoriasis type and duration, and prior treatments. All psoriasis patients underwent comprehensive systemic and dermatological evaluations, including assessments for eyelid lesions associated with psoriasis, nail involvement, and joint symptoms. Patients presenting with joint complaints were referred to a rheumatologist for evaluation of psoriatic arthritis.

The severity of psoriasis was determined using the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI). Healthy individuals with no signs or symptoms of psoriasis and without a family history of the disease were recruited as the control group. Systemic and dermatological evaluations of the control participants were also conducted.

Ophthalmological assessments, including biomicroscopic examination, Schirmer I test, and tear break-up time (BUT) measurements, were performed on both eyes of all participants, with evaluations conducted by an ophthalmologist.

Continuous variables were analyzed using the t-test, while categorical data were compared using

the chi-square test. Logistic regression analysis was employed to explore associations between ocular findings and variables. Statistical evaluations were conducted separately for the right and left eyes.

Results

The study comprised 134 participants (Table 1), with a slightly higher proportion of females than males. The mean age of the participants was 41.20 ± 11.70 years, and the average duration of psoriasis was 119.40 ± 87.20 months. The mean Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) was 8.20 ± 5.50 , indicating a moderate severity of psoriasis in the study population. Ocular involvement was also observed, with 6.72% of participants affected in the right eyelid and 5.97% in the left eyelid.

Logistic regression analysis was performed to determine factors influencing ocular findings (Table 2 and 3). None of the factors analyzed, including gender, age, and duration of psoriasis, PASI, nail involvement, psoriatic arthritis, or eyelid involvement, showed statistically significant associations with ocular findings. The odds ratios (OR) were close to 1, suggesting that these variables did not have a strong effect on ocular manifestations. Tables 4 and 5 compares ocular findings between cases (those with psoriasis) and controls (those without psoriasis). Blepharitis was significantly more common in the case group. Conjunctivitis and corneal involvement were also significantly more prevalent in the case group. No significant difference was found in anterior uveitis or cataract. The total ocular involvement was significantly higher in the psoriasis group.

Schirmer test values were significantly lower in the case group compared to controls for both eyes (Table 6). These findings suggest that individuals with psoriasis have reduced tear production compared to controls, indicating potential ocular dryness or dysfunction.

Table 1: Basic clinicodemographic variables among study population

Characteristic	n	%
Female	70	52.24
Male	64	47.76
Age (mean \pm SD)	41.20 \pm 11.70 years	
Duration of Psoriasis (mean \pm SD)	119.40 \pm 87.20 months	
Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) (mean \pm SD)	8.20 \pm 5.50	
Involvement of Nails	63	47.01
Psoriatic Arthritis	16	11.94
Involvement of Right Eyelid	9	6.72
Involvement of Left Eyelid	8	5.97

Table 2: Logistic regression analysis of factors affecting ocular findings (right eye)

Factor	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-Value
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Gender	1.46	0.630–3.650	0.336
Age	1.03	0.994–1.065	0.123
Duration of Psoriasis	1.003	0.996–1.006	0.642
Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI)	1.02	0.920–1.115	0.58
Involvement of Nails	0.71	0.280–1.690	0.421
Psoriatic Arthritis	0.51	0.110–2.150	0.368
Involvement of Right Eyelid	0.92	0.165–5.100	0.97

Table 3: Logistic regression analysis of factors affecting ocular findings (left eye)

Factor	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-Value
Gender	1.9	0.800–4.450	0.166
Age	1.03	0.995–1.065	0.104
Duration of Psoriasis	1.002	0.997–1.007	0.744
PASI	1.015	0.920–1.110	0.807
Involvement of Nails	0.73	0.290–1.750	0.439
Psoriatic Arthritis	0.245	0.044–1.310	0.092
Involvement of Left Eyelid	3.000	0.410–21.500	0.304

Table 4: Ocular involvement findings of right eye

Findings	Cases	Control	P-Value
Anterior Uveitis	3	–	0.51
Blepharitis	51	24	<0.05
Cataract	7	3	0.47
Conjunctivitis	19	4	<0.05
Corneal Involvement	21	3	<0.05
Episcleritis	1	–	1
Pigment Dispersion	1	–	1
Total	105	34	<0.01

Table 5: Ocular involvement findings of left eye

Findings	Cases	Control	P-Value
Anterior Uveitis	3	–	1
Blepharitis	54	24	<0.05
Cataract	7	3	0.49
Conjunctivitis	19	4	<0.05
Corneal Involvement	21	3	<0.05
Cystoid Macular Edema	1	–	1
Episcleritis	1	–	1
Pigment Dispersion	3	–	1
Total	109	34	<0.01

Table 6: Schirmer values among study groups

Side	Cases	Control	P-Value
Right Eye	14.71 ± 7.51	18.45 ± 6.00	<0.01
Left Eye	14.71 ± 7.59	18.19 ± 6.02	<0.01

Discussion

Ocular involvement in psoriasis is not a widely documented issue, with only a limited number of case reports and studies addressing it [4–8]. The association between psoriasis severity and ocular findings has shown variable results. Some studies reported an increased incidence of ocular findings with greater psoriasis severity [4,10] while others found no such correlation [6]. In our analysis, no statistically significant relationship was observed between ocular findings and PASI scores. This suggests that ocular symptoms should be

considered across all psoriasis cases, regardless of severity. Psoriasis-related ocular involvement has often been reported in conjunction with joint manifestations. Contrary to previous findings, our study did not establish a statistically significant association between joint involvement and ocular findings [11]. Uveitis, however, is frequently linked with joint involvement according to earlier studies [12]. Nail involvement is a recognized marker in patients with psoriatic arthritis [13] leading us to investigate its potential association with ocular findings. Although prior research

suggested a higher prevalence of ocular findings, particularly uveitis, in patients with psoriatic arthritis, our study did not identify a statistically significant relationship between nail involvement and ocular symptoms.

In psoriasis, eyelid-related conditions such as blepharitis, seborrhic changes, loss of eyelashes, and psoriatic plaques may occur. Blepharitis may arise from lachrymal obstruction caused by inadvertent movement of skin scales towards the lacrimal gland during activities like washing or rubbing the eyes [14]. Similar to previous studies, blepharitis was the most frequently observed ocular condition in our patient cohort [10]. When compared to the control group, blepharitis was significantly more prevalent among patients with psoriasis.

Chronic nonspecific conjunctivitis is another common ocular condition in psoriasis. Karabulut et al. demonstrated early conjunctival changes and squamous metaplasia in mild to moderate psoriasis cases using conjunctival impression cytology.

These alterations were attributed to chronic mechanical irritation and suggested a shared etiology between ocular and skin manifestations [15]. In our study, the patient group exhibited a significantly higher rate of conjunctivitis compared to controls. Corneal involvement in psoriasis can occur as a result of dryness, trichiasis, or conjunctival disease [16]. Compared to controls, our study found a significantly higher rate of corneal involvement in the psoriasis group.

Uveitis, particularly associated with psoriatic arthritis or severe pustular psoriasis, has been reported at rates ranging from 2% to 20%. The condition is predominantly anterior, bilateral, and recurrent. Complications such as posterior synechiae, hypopyon, and cystoid macular edema are potential consequences of uveitis [17–21]. While ocular involvement in psoriasis is acknowledged, its underlying etiology remains insufficiently explored. It is generally hypothesized that the mechanisms leading to ocular findings in psoriasis mirror those responsible for cutaneous lesions.

Conclusion

This study demonstrated a higher prevalence of ocular findings in patients with psoriasis compared to healthy controls, alongside significantly reduced Schirmer and tear break-up time (BUT) values. Given the potential for ocular involvement, regular ophthalmologic evaluations are recommended for individuals with psoriasis.

Additionally, it is crucial to consider the possibility of asymptomatic ocular involvement, which may occur independently of other factors. Further research is warranted to better understand the

underlying mechanisms contributing to ocular manifestations in psoriasis.

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